

SMARANDACHE “CHOPPED” N^N AND $N + 1^{N-1}$

Jason Earls
RR 1 Box 43-5, Fritch, Texas 79036

Florentin Smarandache has posed many problems that deal with perfect powers. See [1] for example. Perfect powers of the form N^N are aesthetically pleasing because of their symmetry. But in my opinion they would be more agreeable if their number of decimal digits (their "length" in base-10 representation) were equal to N . In this note we will consider numbers of the form N^N and $N + 1^{N-1}$ that have been "chopped off" to have N decimal digits. We will refer to these numbers as Smarandache Chopped N^N numbers, and Smarandache Chopped $N + 1^{N-1}$ numbers; and we will investigate them to see if 1) they are prime, 2) they are automorphic.

§1 Smarandache Chopped N^N Numbers

There are only three numbers of the form N^N that do not need to be chopped. That is, their decimal length is already equal to N : $11 = 1$, $88 = 16777216$, and $99 = 387420489$. It is easy to see that there will be no more naturally equal to N . For example, 613613 has 1709 digits, 12341234 has 3815 digits; as we progress the decimal lengths continue to increase.

Definition: Smarandache Chopped N^N numbers are numbers formed from the first N digits of N^N . We will call this sequence $SC(n)$:

$$\begin{aligned} n &= 1, & 2, & 3, & 4, & 5, & 6, & 7, & 8, & 9, \\ SC(n) &= 1, & x, & x, & x, & x, & x, & x, & 1677216, & 387420489, \\ n &= & 10, & & 11, & & 12, & & & \\ SC(n) &= & 1000000000, & & 28531167061, & & 891610044825, & & & \\ n &= & 13, & \dots & & & & & & \\ SC(n) &= & 3028751065922, & \dots & & & & & & \end{aligned}$$

For $n = 2$ through 7, $SC(n)$ is not defined, since those values lack one digit of being the proper length. Now we shall consider whether any terms of the

$SC(n)$ sequence are prime, and automorphic. A prime number surely requires no definition here, but perhaps an automorphic number[2] does. The term automorphic is usually applied to squares, but here we broaden the definition a bit. An automorphic number is a positive integer defined by some function, f , whose functional value terminates with the digits of n . For example, if $f(n) = n^2$, then 76 is automorphic because $76^2 = 5776$ ends with 76.

Concerning the question of which Smarandache Chopped N^N numbers are prime, a computer program was written, and $SC(65)$ and $SC(603)$ were discovered and proved to be prime. No more were found up to $n = 3000$. Question: Are there infinitely many SC primes?

Concerning the question of which Smarandache Chopped N^N numbers are automorphic, a computer program was written, and when $n = 1, 9, 66,$ and $6051,$ $SC(n)$ is automorphic. No more were found up to $n = 20000$. Question: Are there infinitely many SC automorphic numbers?

Here is $SC(66)$ to demonstrate that it is automorphic:

$$SC(66) = 12299848035352374253574605798249524538486099538968 \\ 2130228631906566$$

§2 Smarandache Chopped $N - 1^{N+1}$ Numbers

Numbers formed from the first N digits of $N - 1^{N+1}$ also have an intriguing symmetry. There are only three numbers of the form $N - 1^{N+1}$ that do not need to be chopped: $0^2 = 0,$ $6^8 = 1679616,$ and $7^9 = 40353607$. It is easy to see that there will be no more that are naturally equal to N . We will call this sequence $SC2(n)$.

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc} n = & 1, & 2, & 3, & 4, & 5, & 6, & 7, & 8, \\ SC2(n) = & 0, & x, & x, & x, & x, & x, & 1679616, & 40353607, \\ n = & & & & 9, & 10, & & & 11, \dots \\ SC2(n) = & 107374182, & 3138105960, & & & & & & 10000000000, \dots \end{array}$$

Primes: A program was written, and $SC2(44), SC2(64),$ and $SC2(1453)$ were discovered and proved to be prime. No more were found up to $n = 3000$. Question: Are there infinitely many $SC2$ primes?

Automorphics: A program was written, and $SC2(9416)$ was the only term discovered to be automorphic. No more were found up to $n = 20000$. Question: Are there infinitely many $SC2$ automorphic numbers?

§3 Additional Questions

1. Do these sequences, $SC(n)$ and $SC2(n)$, defy basic analysis because of their "chopped" property?
2. What other properties do the $SC(n)$ and $SC2(n)$ sequences have?

References

[1] F. Smarandache, *Only Problems, Not Solutions*, Xiquan Publishing House, Chicago, 1993.

[2] Eric W. Weinstein, Automorphic Number, From MathWorld - A Wolfram Web Resource. <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/AutomorphicNumber.html>